

kg P/ha and 33.2 kg K/ha were applied. Prilled urea was applied as basal in 2-3 cm standing water.

Root zone placement (10-12 cm) of urea supergranules (USG) and basal sulfur-coated-urea (SCU) and Mussooriephos-coated urea (MPCU) at

58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha were evaluated against local best split (1/2 basal + 1/4 at maximum tillering + 1/4 at panicle initiation) and standard best split (2/3 basal + 1/3 at panicle initiation).

Maximum grain yield was with USG and SCU at all N levels (see table). USG

produced significantly higher yields than standard best split urea and MPCU at 87 and 116 kg N/ha. USG and SCU also produced significantly more panicles/m² than MPCU at 116 kg N/ha. □

Nitrogen management for increasing N efficiency in transplanted rice

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We compared the efficiency of a single application of sulfur-coated urea (SCU), urea supergranules (USG), and split application of prilled urea (PU) at

varying levels of N during 1983 kharif. The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Treatments were SCU, USG, and PU at 29, 58, 87, and 116 kg N/ha. Medium-duration, dwarf variety Usha was the test crop. Soil was a Vertisol (clay-loam, with 210.11 kg available N, 12.50 kg available P, 225 kg available K/ha, 0.20 mmho EC, 0.60% organic C, and pH 6.5-7.5).

Growth and yield-contributing characters were significantly superior with SCU and USG (see table). Grain

and straw yields were significantly different with different forms and levels of N.

Maximum grain yield was with SCU, followed by USG. SCU and USG were similar in N efficiency. USG produced a significantly higher straw yield than SCU and PU.

N at 116 kg/ha produced significantly high grain and straw yields. □

Grain yield and ancillary characters as influenced by sources and levels of N. Raipur, India, 1983 kharif.

Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Sources and methods of N application	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Effective tillers/m ²	Panicle weight (g)	Panicle length (cm)	Sound spikelets/panicle
0	Check	1.9	2.30	190	1.3	17	48
29	Urea, best split	2.6	2.94	206	1.7	18	62
29	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	3.2	3.51	259	2.1	20	69
29	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	3.2	3.77	257	1.8	19	66
	Mean	3.0	3.40	240	1.9	19	65
58	Urea, best split	3.0	3.15	243	1.9	19	67
58	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	3.8	4.35	304	2.2	21	76
58	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	3.7	4.97	303	2.1	20	70
	Mean	3.5	4.16	283	2.1	20	71
87	Urea, best split	3.3	3.50	277	1.9	19	68
87	SCU, broadcast and incorporated in soil	4.2	5.30	344	2.3	21	79
87	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	4.1	5.84	340	2.2	21	76
	Mean	3.9	4.88	320	2.2	20	75
116	Urea, best split	3.7	4.32	335	2.1	20	72
116	SCU broadcast and incorporated in soil	4.5	6.24	409	2.5	22	82
116	USG placed at 10-12 cm soil depth	4.3	6.97	405	2.4	22	80
	Mean	4.2	5.84	383	2.3	21	78
	CD (0.05) for forms	0.2	0.40	9	0.1	0.4	5.7
	for levels	0.2	0.46	10	0.2	0.5	6.6

Nitrogen sources for flooded rice

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We evaluated prilled urea (PU), neem cake coated-urea (NCU), lac-coated urea (LCU), didin-coated urea (DCU), and urea supergranule (USG) at 40, 80, and 120 kg N/ha for transplanted rice in the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons. Experimental field soil was a fine, silty, mixed, hyperthermic, Typic Hapludoll with pH

Effect of N source and N level on yield. Pantnagar, India, 1983 and 1984 wet seasons.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	1983	1984	Mean
<i>N sources</i>			
PU	3.67	3.71	3.69
NCU	4.36	4.57	4.46
LCU	3.79	4.14	3.96
DCU	3.71	4.11	3.91
USG	4.70	4.73	4.72
SE	0.06	0.06	—
CD (0.05)	0.16	0.16	—
<i>N levels (kg/ha)</i>			
0	2.25	2.42	2.33
40	3.36	3.55	3.45
80	4.11	4.36	4.24
120	4.66	4.91	4.78
SE	0.04	0.04	—
CD (0.05)	0.12	0.12	—

7.6, 1.2% organic C, 44 kg available P/ha, and 313 kg available K/ha. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design.

One-half the PU was applied at transplanting and one-half equally divided into two topdressings at tillering and panicle initiation. NCU, LCU, and DCU were applied one-half at

transplanting and one-half at tillering. USG was placed 8-10 cm deep in the center of 4 hills 1 wk after transplanting. All plots received 17.4 kg P and 33.3 kg K/ha. Two seedlings per hill of rice variety Jaya were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing. The field was flooded (5 cm ± 3 cm) by rain or irrigation from

transplanting to milk stage.

N levels and N sources significantly influenced yield (see table). All amended N fertilizers except DCU in 1983 performed better than PU in both years. USG outyielded other N sources, with 28% higher yield than PU in 1983 and 27.5% higher in 1984. □

Effect of transplanting date and N application on yield

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Under optimal water and minerals, applied N absorption by rice and its translation into grain yield are limited by such climatic factors as light and temperature. Transplanting date and crop duration seem to be important. We studied yield response to applied N at different transplanting dates.

The experiment was in a Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.5, 0.24% organic C, and 0.03% total N. Four levels of N (0, 60, 120, and 180 kg/ha) were used in a split-plot design. PR106 seedlings at 45 d were transplanted on 9 Jun, 30 Jun, and 21 Jul at 15- × 15-cm spacing. Field plots were submerged 2 d before the

transplanting. Crop durations were 121, 112, and 101 d.

Although response to applied N was significant, transplanting date had a pronounced effect on the nature and extent of the response (see figure). Rice transplanted 9 Jun and 30 Jun and harvested at 121 and 112 d exhibited quadratic response curves that were almost flat with 180 kg N/ha. Rice transplanted 21 Jul matured in only 101 d and responded linearly, with lower yields than the crops transplanted in Jun, at least up to 180 kg N/ha. The influence of transplanting date and N was reflected primarily in tiller density and spikelet number.

The interaction between N level and date of transplanting was significant. Yield similar to those with 180 kg N/ha and 21 Jul transplanting could be obtained with 120 kg N/ha and 30 Jun transplanting or 60 kg N/ha and 9 Jun transplanting. □

Effect of slow-release nitrogen fertilizers on lowland rice

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We studied five sources of N during the 1984 wet season (WS) in a split-plot design with three replications. N levels were in the main plots and sources in the subplots. The soil was lateritic and sandy loam, pH 5.8, EC 0.112 dS/m, 0.73% organic C, 0.07% total N, 20 kg available P, and 140 kg available K/ha. Rice varieties were Lalat (135 d) during the WS and Jajati (120 d) during the dry season (DS). Spacing was 15 × 10 cm.

All N sources were applied in a single dose at transplanting except for prilled urea, which was split-applied: 25% at transplanting, 50% at tillering, and 25%

Effect of N source on yield and BB intensity. Bhubaneswar, India, 1984-85.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		BB ^a	
	WS	DS	WS	DS
N level				
No N	1.9	2.2	2	2
56 kg/ha	2.9	2.7	3	2
84 kg/ha	3.0	2.8	4	3
112 kg/ha	3.3	2.7	4	3
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.3	-	-
CV (%)	45	-	-	-
Source				
Prilled urea split application	3.0	2.5	3	2
Urea gypsum	3.0	2.8	3	2
Rock phosphate-coated urea	3.0	2.6	3	2
Urea supergranule	3.3	2.9	4	2
Urea nitro-humic acid	3.0	2.8	3	2
CD (0.05)	0.2	0.3	-	-
CV (%)	6	6	-	-

^aStandard evaluation system for rice scale.

Effect of transplanting date on lowland rice response to N. Ludhiana, India.